

Characterization of Silicon-based Fibers Prepared by Electrospinning for Potential Li-ion Battery Anodes

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Abstract

The rapid growth of electric vehicles (EVs) is driven by advances in lithium-ion batteries (LIBs), particularly in anode materials. Graphite electrodes, widely used for their high porosity, conductivity, low weight, and cost-effectiveness, face competition from monocrystalline silicon. Silicon anodes offer higher capacity and energy density, and they are safer because of their nonflammable nature. However, silicon's tendency to expand and contract during cycling presents challenges. This study explores the use of silicon nano- and microfibers to enhance battery stability, addressing these issues effectively.

Monocrystalline silicon particles, obtained through milling and sieving, were used as the active component in the nanofibers. These particles, combined with organic precursors (PVP and TEOS), were processed using electrospinning to form fibers. The fibers were then annealed at 650 °C to remove the polymeric PVP component.

The results provide valuable insights into the properties and interactions of the silicon nanofibers, highlighting their potential in advanced energy storage devices.

Keywords

Silicon-based anode, fibers, Li-ion battery, electrospinning, energy storage and conversion

1. Introduction

An anode represents a key element in rechargeable batteries, which significantly influences overall battery performance. Presently, because of its layered structure, graphite is a widely used material for commercially available anodes. This structure is characterised by a layered arrangement with relatively large gaps between adjacent layers of carbon atoms, providing sites for lithium ion insertion. This process prevents changes in the shape, size, and structure of the anodic material during the charging and discharging phases. To improve all parameters that affect battery performance, efforts are underway to replace graphite with alternative, superior materials [1-3].

Silicon-based compounds are highly promising for lithium-ion battery anodes due to their excellent gravimetric and volumetric capacities, favourable economic prospects, and safer low working potential compared to graphite anodes. Silicon's ability to transition from a crystalline to an amorphous phase during the initial charge-discharge cycle is particularly intriguing. However, widespread adoption is hindered by a rapid capacity drop of up to 10% within the first 10 cycles. Despite challenges such as volumetric expansion and low electrical conductivity, silicon remains a top candidate for high-energy-density batteries. Future efforts aim to enhance capacity and cycling stability of silicon-based anodes [1, 4, 5].

Nanometre-scale materials offer significant advances for lithium-ion batteries by reducing diffusion pathways for lithium ions, a critical limitation of current batteries using micrometre-sized particles with minimal surface area. This reduction enhances charging and discharging rates. Transitioning to nanometre-sized particles significantly increases lithium storage capacity. Nanostructured electrodes, with their hierarchical nanometre-scale architecture, enable shortened diffusion lengths and improve electrode kinetics. Additionally, they introduce new lithium storage

mechanisms on the electrode surface, boosting capacity, flexibility, and cycling stability. In our research, fibres were prepared using the electrospinning method, which requires a high-voltage power source and precise process parameter adjustments to optimize the properties of the starting solutions and resulting fibres [6-8].

2. Experimental procedure

Preparation of material

As a first step of the experiment, silicon monocrystal particles were prepared by milling in a planetary ball mill (E-Max) at a speed of 600 rpm for 10 minutes. The milling was performed dry in a zirconia jar, followed by sieving the particles through a 40 μm sieve. The particle size distribution was determined for the ground particles before mixing. These prepared particles were then mixed with other components of the fiber solution—polyvinylpyrrolidone solution (PVP in EtOH) and tetraethylorthosilicate solution (TEOS + HCl + H₂O) in a ratio of TEOS : PVP : particles 2 : 2.5 : 1 (TEOS and PVP from Sigma, EtOH and HCl from Lachner). The resulting solution was left to mature in the refrigerator at a temperature of 5 °C for a predetermined period to facilitate the polymerization of TEOS. After two months, it was transferred to a syringe, part of the electrospinning system EF050 Needle Starter Kit (SKE Research Equipment) capable of producing fiber layers through high-voltage application. The applied voltage was 20 kV, the distance from the collector was 15 cm, and the viscosity of the suspensions was 0.141 Pa·s. The resulting layers were approximately 10x10 cm in size. These prepared layers were analysed by XRD, XRF, and thermogravimetric analysis and were also observed using scanning electron microscopy. Subsequently, the layers were sintered at 650 °C for 1 hour, and almost all analyses were repeated.

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3. Results and discussion

The particles, which were modified by milling in a planetary ball mill and subsequently sieved, were subjected to **particle size distribution analysis**. Figure 1 presents the results of the particle size distribution analysis conducted using a confocal microscope LEXT OLS 5000 SAF (Olympus). The analysis revealed that the median particle size is $d_{50} = 7.17 \mu\text{m}$ and majority of monocrystalline silicon particles fall within a size range centred around a diameter of 7-8 μm . The analysis was performed repeatedly, and the presented results described at least 5000 particles.

Figure 1: Particle size distribution of monocrystalline silicon particles.

The layers of prepared fibers were analysed in terms of their chemical and phase composition, specifically using **X-ray diffraction and fluorescence analysis**. These measurements were conducted before and after firing to better map the changes that occurred in the material upon exposure to high temperatures.

Table 1: XRF analysis of fibre layers before and after sintering.

<i>Before sintering (SiAN)</i>		<i>After sintering (SiAV)</i>	
elements	chemical composition (wt.%)	elements	chemical composition (wt.%)
Si	99.31 ± 0.10	Si	99.64 ± 0.08
Zr	0.03 ± 0.01	Zr	0.06 ± 0.01
Cl	0.43 ± 0.02	Cl	0.04 ± 0.01
As	0.12 ± 0.01	Al	0.03 ± 0.01
Others	0.11 ± 0.01	Others	0.23 ± 0.01

Figure 2: a) XRD analysis of fiber layers before and b) XRD after sintering.

Figure 2a) shows a comparison of the chemical composition with XRF (WD-XRF Axios, PANalytical) of the sintered and unsintered fibres. The table 1 presents the results in terms of elemental composition. Since one of the main components is the fibre forming TEOS, which contains silicon, and the fibres are additionally filled with silicon particles, it is evident that the predominant chemical composition of the fibres is silicon both before and after thermal exposure. The presence of other minor elements is attributed to the lower purity of the silicon particles used. Chlorine is present due to the use of HCl in the preparation of solutions for the fibres. The slight increase in silicon content after firing is due to the removal of other minor components and the additional polymer required for fibre preparation—PVP—during the firing process, which proportionally increases the silicon content. Since the goal is to achieve the highest concentration of silicon in the fibres, this phenomenon is desirable. The results are normalized, and oxygen was not detected.

Phase changes were analysed using XRD (Fig. 2b,c) (PANalytical X'Pert Pro, PANalytical) focussing on the fiber layers before sintering (SiAun) and after firing (SiAsint). In the unsintered sample an amorphous region was observed, caused by the presence of the polymer PVP. During thermal exposure, this polymer is removed from the fiber layer, and thus in the diffraction pattern of the sintered sample, no amorphous region is detected. The absence of the amorphous phase

also resulted in an increase in the intensities of the other peaks, indicating a crystalline phase, which was identified as crystalline silicon (ICDD 04-006-2527) on the basis of database comparisons.

The fibres prepared from 2 mL of solution were observed in secondary electrons mode using a **scanning electron microscope SEM VEGA 3 LMU (TESCAN)**.

Figure 3: Images from scanning electron microscope of a) fibres before sintering b) after sintering.

Figures 3a) and 3b) present images captured by a SEM. In Figure 3a), fibres are shown before thermal exposure, with the width of the fibres in the foreground estimated to be 1 μm . The widths of other fibres may be distorted due to the distance and overlap. At this stage, silicon particles are not prominently visible, likely because of the persistent presence of PVP. In Figure 3b), fibres are observed after thermal treatment at 650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, showing fibres with varying diameters, generally smaller than those of the untreated samples. Particles are more visible on these fibres, appearing as growths on the surface of the individual fibres. Additionally, structures formed during the sintering process can also be observed in the image.

Since it is suitable to sinter the material when preparing fibers for the anode, it was appropriate to subject the material to **simultaneous thermal analysis combined with mass spectroscopy** using a Setsys Evolution apparatus (Setaram). The analysis was conducted with a flow rate of 50 mL/min and a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ in a dynamic air atmosphere. This approach was used to detect changes during the sintering process itself.

Figure 4: a) TGA analysis of fibres prior to sintering and b) relative intensity of released gases

The curve illustrating the changes associated with mass loss during sintering can be divided into four regions. In the region between 50 °C and 176 °C, moisture is released [9]. The next step, occurring between 176 °C and 376 °C, features an exothermic peak at 350 °C due to the decomposition of organic components (TEOS) and the side chains of PVP. The following region, from 376 °C to 614 °C, contains another exothermic peak due to the release of the main chains of PVP. In the final region, above 614 °C, there is a slight increase in mass due to the oxidation of silicon to SiO₂. In general, the mass loss during firing up to 1000 °C is approximately 40 %, with the majority of the loss occurring at 650 °C.

4. Conclusions

The preparation of fibres infused with monocrystalline silicon using high-voltage electrospinning represents an innovative approach to producing advanced anode materials for lithium-ion batteries. The analysed layers show promising properties, with chemical and phase composition analyses confirming the successful removal of the PVP polymer matrix after sintering. Silicon, as an anode material, offers significant advantages due to its high energy density, non-flammability, and approximately ten times higher theoretical capacity compared to commonly used graphite. Given these properties, it is a suitable material for anodes. Moreover, the fibrous form of the anode provides increased flexibility, ensuring greater stability during cycling. These characteristics suggest that monocrystalline silicon fibres have the potential to significantly

enhance the performance and safety of future lithium-ion batteries, making this approach promising for commercial applications in the energy sector.

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